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ANALYSIS OF MIRIAM D. SANTIAGO'S PICK-UP LINES AS POPULAR CULTURE: PROPOSED LESSON DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the top ten pick-up lines as a situational linguistic form of popular culture based on the context, symbolism, theme, and values that can be used as one of the strategies of teachers in teaching inter-active learning specifically in the Filipino language. This study attempts to study and analyze pick-up lines as popular culture used by millennials to be used as a basis for enriching the language by using them in classroom discussions.

The researcher collected the pick-up lines popularized by Sen. Miriam Santiago, who impressed the minds of Filipinos, especially the young Filipinos, better known as millennials, who are often used on social media.

A mixed methodology was used in the study. Qualitative and quantitative (Creswell, 2009) is an approach based on the assumption that any research is capable of collecting different types of data that will provide the opportunity for a proper understanding of the problem and to see the different angles or perspectives that will be the result of the study. A questionnaire was used to collect data for data analysis.

In this study, Miriam Defensor Santiago's pick-up lines will be analyzed based on the formalistic approach, an approach that focuses on the structure, factors, and elements of poetry and the theme or subject of the work, as well as the sensibility of the correlation of words, language structure, symbolism, and human values that the researcher attached to the Core Values of the Department of Education.

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The symbol stimulates the student's critical thinking to think about what symbol the pick-up line represents. Students will be able to practice critical thinking to be able to think not only with superficial thoughts but also to draw deep answers from the questions brought up by the symbol of Miriam Santiago's pick-up lines.

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